

Editor in Chief

**Dr Adebayo Ola
AFOLARANMI**

Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Editors

**Assoc. Prof Adekunle
Olusola OTUNLA**

Department of Mass
Communication and Media
Technology,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

**Dr Michael
GBADEGESIN**

Department of Languages
and Literature
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Associate Editors

**Dr Emmanuel O.
MALOMO**

ECWA Gospel Centre,
Kano, Nigeria

**Rebecca Oluwatosin
BANJO**

Department of Peace
Studies and Conflicts
Resolution, Ajayi Crowther
University, Oyo, Nigeria

**Dr Emmanuel Selome
FASINU**

Department of Political
Science, Wesley University,
Ondo, Nigeria

**An Appraisal of Pastoral Leadership
Response to Criticism in the Redeemed
College of Missions, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria**

Oluwaseun Stephen OLUOKUN

*Department of Politics and International
Relations, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo
State, Nigeria*

oluokun.oluwaseun@lcu.edu.ng, +2347068727860,
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1473-7712>

Ayodele Adeyinka ATOWOJU, Ph.D.

*Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria*
atowoju.avodele@lcu.edu.ng, +2348036726849,
<https://oraid.org/0009-0004-2439-2472>

Abstract

In leadership positions, criticism is unavoidable, but many leaders reject criticism passionately. Criticism no doubt can make or mar a leader's life, depending on how it is handled. Previous studies have looked at what influences how people react to painful situations, including the feelings that cause rage and other negative emotions. Most recently, several literatures have been written on the pastoral and administrative life of church leaders. However, scholarly research has not been adequately carried out on the appraisal of Pastoral Leadership Response to Criticism in the Redeemed College of Missions, Ede. The paper used the descriptive research design with the B. F Skinner Theory of Reinforcement as the theoretical Framework. The purposive and simple random techniques were used to select 150 participants. Nevertheless, only one hundred and forty-one (141) copies of the questionnaire were retrieved. Data collected were analysed using simple descriptive statistics. The findings show that Christian leaders'

responses to criticism are characterized by both hostility and calmness, but the source, methods and structure of criticisms have in-depth impact on the leader's interpretation and responses to the criticisms. Conclusively, the study have proven that Leaders in the Redeemed College of Missions, Ede usually respond to criticism whenever necessary but the manner in which criticism is framed usually influenced the leader's interpretation and responses. It is therefore recommended, that Leaders in every organization, particularly the church, should develop a strong mind-set to deal effectively and positively with criticism and use it as a vehicle for creativity, innovation and further self-development.

Keywords: Christian Pastoral Leadership, Criticism of Pastoral Leadership, Pastor, Redeemed College of Missions, Ede.

Introduction

In leadership positions, criticism is unavoidable, but many leaders reject criticism passionately. Criticism can make or mar a leader's life or ministry, depending on how it is handled. Jesus Christ in His pastoral leadership was criticized. His Apostles were not left out of criticism. Today, many contemporary church leaders have also been criticized in one way or the other. No matter how much care they took in their words, people still find fault in them. Scholars from different backgrounds have written on the life and ministry of the church leaders. Most recently, several pieces of literature have been directed to the administrative life of church leaders, leadership in the Church and the nature of Church leadership in the 21st century (Ayogu , Ribeiro and Leite,2022). Also, Jesus' Model of Leadership and the Integrity of Church Leaders in Nigeria (Igbari, 2021). However, scholarly research has not been thoroughly carried out on the criticism of pastoral leadership in the Redeemed College of Missions, Ededimeji, Ede, Osun State. This paper aims at exploring this with a critical and analytical assessment of the effect of criticism on pastoral leadership with the understanding that it will serve as a template for the Redeemed College of Missions and clerics of other Churches and institutions in Nigeria and other nations.

Pastoral leadership is one of the most difficult positions on Earth due to some of the responsibilities and challenges attached to it. For as long as the Church of God on Earth has been, shepherding people has been a constant responsibility (Mujiono and Wibowo, 2023). The empirical and anecdotal literature on ministry has frequently highlighted the negative perspective that pastoral ministry is a demanding and stressful career (Lee and Rosales,

2020). A church's ability to thrive and maintain its health depends on its pastoral leadership. While ineffective or misdirected leadership can cause a church to fail, competent biblical leadership can propel a church toward evangelistic expansion and successful discipleship (Larry, 2010). In other words, a pastor who is not physically, spiritually and emotionally fit will not have a healthy Church.

However, leaders in all spheres of life, political, social, economic and religious are prone to criticism at different times and for different reasons. This is the expression of displeasure towards someone or something because of defects, complaints, or errors that are thought to exist. If criticism is not handled well, it may turn an articulate and well engaged pastor into a silent one. Leadership is essential in today's globally competitive workforce, hence a church needs a leader who can handle and comprehend the complexity of the world (Saleh, Nusari, Ameen and Alrajawy, 2018).

Even though Jesus was flawless during His time here, criticism was linked to His work. However, despite all of the critiques directed at Him during His life and ministry, Jesus Christ was able to triumph by using the principles of leadership. He was able to finish His assignment on earth strong and healthy. It is often quite hard to take criticism well or be around critical individuals.

Pastors should be aware that it is hard to please and win every body, particularly when attempting to persuade them to make changes in their lives (Pastoralcareinc,2022). People generally expect leaders to act in a way that satisfies and makes them happy. One of the main reasons for criticism is that a leader cannot satisfy everyone. If care is not taken, this can cause the leader to become extremely frustrated.

In every Church there will be people who are not very appreciative, envious and who usually just critically or presumptively rejects the personality and activities of a particular leader(s) in an establishment or organization. And for all pastors, this should be expected at different stages of one's pastoral ministry. It follows that if you are a pastor, you will undoubtedly face criticism even from unexpected quarters. You could face criticism from people who are part of your church, from those who are not, and even from total strangers. Both friends and foes will voice their criticism at will. There will be criticism that is factual in parts, untrue in others, and maybe even evil and malicious. This shows that criticism is inevitable in pastoral work (Mahaney, 2022). Moreover, most criticism could end in causing emotional

harms and irreparable damages. This is why people fear it and desire a considerable freedom from it. But life's events remind one of its all-consuming barades of criticism in pastoral ministry. "When one is bombarded by the missiles and in-depth charges of criticism from friends and foes," "it often has a devastating effect on the emotions of its victims. This could completely disrupt the victim's work and should be dealt with utmost understanding." In other words, human nature is prone to conflicts, fighting, and anger.

Some of the reasons for criticism include: jealousy, unmet expectations, misunderstanding, organizational crisis, values conflict, failure, distrust, pride and arrogance. However, whenever criticisms come from pure intention, the results will be positive and relationships will improve. But the most common criticisms are the ones that causes emotional distress which usually leads to negative reactions. Hans lists the following responses to criticism: quit, run, hide, get angry, get depressed, get revenge, fight back, and ignore critics (Hans, 1998). Jesus Christ left an example of total faith in God's honesty and justice. People insulted him, but he did not insult them. He suffered, but he never threatened anyone. No, he let God take care of him. God is the one who judges correctly (Holy Bible: Easy-to-Read Version, 2005).

Additionally, Pastor E. A. Adeboye has been criticized on several occasions by members of the Redeemed Christian Church and the general public. These criticisms include buying a private jet, the university and other school's expensive tuitions, management of funds, his administrative skill, traffic jams on the Lagos-Ibadan highway that last for hours whenever there are church activities, and Clinging to church leadership for long, even after turning 75 years and despite having been General Overseer since 1981. These were said to discredit all his efforts at developing the Church. However, his life and ministry has not been adversely affected by the criticism (Ecomium, 2017). Pastor Adeboye explained his reasons for not replying his numerous critics, that:

As an ambassador of Jesus Christ he only prays for his critics and that his defense and security are embedded in God. Anybody who is attacking the ambassador of Christ is only asking the Consuming Fire to fight his enemies (Vanguard, 2018).

Theoretical Framework

Reinforcement Theory – B F Skinner

The Effects of Criticism on Pastoral Leadership can be further explained using the Theory of Reinforcement in B.F. Skinner's work which is based on the assumption that actions are influenced by their consequences. Reinforcement theory is the process of shaping behaviour by controlling its consequences. Reinforcement theory suggests that you can change someone's behaviour through reinforcement, punishment, and inhibition. Rewards are used to reinforce desired behaviour, while punishments are used to discourage unwanted behaviour. Extinction is a means of preventing someone from performing a learned behaviour. The technical term for this process is “operant conditioning.” Reinforcement can be divided into positive reinforcement and negative reinforcement as follows:

Positive reinforcement occurs when the consequences of the behaviour you are trying to induce increase the likelihood that the desired behaviour will continue. Salespeople can receive bonuses when they perform well, which increases their desire to sell due to positive results. Negative reinforcement occurs when a negative consequence is withheld when the desired behaviour occurs, increasing the likelihood that the desired behaviour will continue. For example, let's say your company is opening a new office in the Outer Hebrides. No one wants to move there. The company decided to give the office's 10 top salespeople a choice between moving to the Outer Hebrides or staying at their existing office. You work hard to avoid the negative consequences of moving there to get into the top ten. We will continue to make every possible effort to avoid negative consequences. However, negative reinforcement is not the same as punishment. Reinforcement theory proposes that when positive reinforcement for a learned response is withdrawn, people continue to practice that behaviour over some time. However, over time, if the lack of reinforcement continues, the frequency and intensity of the behaviour will decrease and eventually disappear (Skinner,2017).

Concept of Criticism

The word, criticism comes from the French word, critique; in the 14th century. Criticism is a word used in two senses; it initially meant, scholarly inquiry and coordinated judgment". The words “critic” and “critical” have existed in the English language since the mid-16th century. The word

"criticism" first appeared in English in the mid-17th century. Soon after in the mid-20th century, the word came to mean unfriendly attack" indicating the horrific nature of the subject (Sekhar Rao, 2020).

A contemporary dictionary defines criticism as follows: the act of criticizing, which is typically done negatively; the art of assessing or analyzing literary or artistic works; writings that express such an assessment or analysis; the scientific study of literary documents (like the Bible) concerning issues like composition, history, origin, text, or textual details. an assessment made of something or someone, especially one that is unfavourable, or the process of making such assessments; A critical analysis or statement of disapproval of anything to assess its quality or clarify its meaning is sometimes referred to as criticism (Contemporary dictionary,2020). When criticism of this nature is constructive it can make an individual aware of gaps in their understanding. It can also provide distinct routes for improvement, Research supports the notion that using feedback in the learning process has a very powerful impact (Wisniewski, Zierer and Hattie, 2020). Using constructive criticism in the learning process also has a huge impact (Lonneke Schellekens, Harold Bok, Lubberta de Jong, Marieke van der Schaaf, Wim Kremer and Cees van der Vleuten,2021).

Furthermore, criticism is described as unfavourable assessment feedback that one receives from people in social situations: Negative feedback in the form of social judgments, such as social rejection, can cause low self-esteem (Van Houtum Lisanne, Geert-Jan, Wever Mirjam, Janssen Loes, Van Schie Charlotte, Tollenaar Marieke, Elzinga Bernet,2022). It was shown that most narratives of painful incidents contained criticism (Christiane, Jauch, Selma, 2023) This falls under the realm of damaging exchanges in romantic partnerships as well (Solomon and Theiss,2022). However, criticism can also be seen as constructive, which can be understood as advancing knowledge and offering avenues for advancement (Allred and Chambless,2018). To get insight into the detrimental effects of criticism in relationships, it is crucial to look at individual variances in how criticism is perceived in interpersonal interactions.

Types of Criticism

Though criticism comes in many forms, it is always harmful. This can impact someone whether they are at work, at home, or just casually perusing social media. While criticism can be a helpful source of feedback,

it can also be very damaging to one's self-esteem and ruin their day. Everyone has experienced criticism, and we have all given in to the urge to freely voice our thoughts about the actions or inactions of others. When someone criticizes a person, they usually do so by drawing comparisons between him and a standard—either personal or organizational, such as the standard at work—and highlighting the failure to meet that standard. Scientists claim that while it may be simple to avoid criticism by remaining silent, in practice this isn't a practical course of action. Get out there and try to learn and practice the art of giving constructive criticism and handling critical people, rather than hiding under a rock to avoid criticism. There are many types of criticism but five of them will be examine below.

Constructive Criticism

Good criticism is constructive criticism. This is helpful since it highlights errors and illustrates areas for improvement. If we are unaware of our shortcomings, how can we possibly improve and evolve? Rather than discouraging you, constructive criticism should be seen as helpful input that advances your development. Even though it stings a little, it's usually easier to accept constructive criticism. It's human nature for us to make mistakes. We have lots of chances to grow and learn throughout our lives. To get better, we ought to make an effort to consider criticism. Opponents are employed. Consider them sly ally members entrusted with promoting the growth and vigour of your skin. Both professional and personal success must be able to accept criticism in a composed manner. Effective listening enhances academic performance, interpersonal relationships, and negotiation skills—even when it comes to negative opinions.

Destructive Criticism

Destructive criticism, however, is unhealthy. This might be the transgression of someone else who neglected to attend a class on emotional intelligence at school, but it could also be done with deliberate malice and hurt. The idea is to demonstrate the meaninglessness of a person or object. It's intended to shatter you. "If you find yourself the object of any destructive criticism, treat them with equanimity and look at them with utter contempt," the scientist advised. And never forget that they are not deserving of your time"(J Reed,2020).

It is important to remember that not all criticism—whether constructive or destructive—is conveyed gently or harshly. People will occasionally criticize you for remarks you've made or remarks that seem impolite, and after the initial shock wears off and you begin to think clearly, you'll realize that they might be correct. There are occasionally kind and kind people who "innocently" remark on how you looked that day and smile broadly, but their true intentions are to undermine your confidence and sense of self-worth.

Self-Criticism

Self-criticism is that voice in your head that constantly tells you that you are not good enough, that you will never be able to do this or that, and that you are a failure. Self-critical people also often feel guilty, worthless, and inferior. Self-reflection and self-evaluation are two different things. Self-reflection is a fundamental human quality. Self-analysis is useful when it involves a critical assessment of your thoughts, feelings, and behaviours; it can support our wisdom in several ways. Self-reflection aids in self-awareness by allowing us to connect with ourselves and recognize negative patterns in our lives, processes tough emotions, helps us identify our values, and aids in decision-making. An insightful self-evaluation tells you what went wrong and what to do better the next time. Self-criticism, on the other hand, entails destructive, demeaning, and devaluing reflective thought. Self-compassion, self-comfort, and learning how to relax your body and emotions are the antidotes to self-criticism. Self-compassion enables us to accept ourselves more fully—our strengths and all of our shortcomings, imperfections, and mistakes—as we are.

Aesthetics Criticism

This type of criticism is considered a part of aesthetics that deals with the highly critical evaluation of beauty and awareness of style, fashion, and other human emotional issues. Human life has an aesthetic dimension to most aspects of life, which means there are many opportunities for criticism. Architectural criticism is considered the highest form of aesthetic criticism because architecture is a combination of three disciplines: art, science, and technology.

An attractive home environment is created by architects for a place where people spend nearly all of their waking hours. An aesthetic critic would not say 'It's beautiful' or 'It's ugly' and instead aim to elaborate on the meaning

of the work and the reason behind why something is beautiful or ugly. He would also elaborate on how the meaning of a design should be interpreted and if would I get the week's current stronger sides of a cultural object. This explains why a wide range of criteria are employed by aesthetic critics in their commentary. The criteria cover topics like the purpose of the creative endeavour, the context in which it is taking place, the techniques employed to produce the aesthetic effect, the feelings and ideals that the phenomenon communicates visually, the relationship between an object and the object under criticism and its themes, objects, or genres, the interaction and overall effect of the observer and observed, and lastly the role of the criticism. This kind of criterion typically calls for extensive knowledge. By doing this, you can bring attention to problems that most people would prefer to ignore, increase appreciation for artistic merit, and even spark a debate about the aesthetic merits of different expressions.

Factual Criticism

Factual criticism is the term for an objection to a situation or idea that points out flaws in the supporting data. When a fact that is relevant is deemed inaccurate or untrue, it indicates that it has not been proven to be true. Additionally, the facts that are mentioned frequently suggest contradictory narratives that are incomprehensible. It is generally accepted that logical and factual criticism are crucial for guaranteeing the consistency, predictability, and dependability of any course of action. Behaviour needs to be predictable and consistent to have meaning; otherwise, it can cause confusion and disorientation, which makes it difficult for us to make wise decisions.

Because facts are observations derived from the five senses and thus subject to interpretation, they are inherently problematic. The effect, which consists of the interaction between the observer and the observed, is accomplished with the aid of fundamental cognitive classification. Certain facts are indisputable because they are supported by evidence that is consistently perceived by all parties under all circumstances. When it comes to factual criticism, reality matters. It is ineffective to treat factual evidence as a matter of subjective interpretation. This kind of critique presupposes that everyone acknowledges the existence of a reality distinct from personal experience (Bhasin,2019).

Pastoral Leadership

Pastoral leadership can be defined and discussed in a variety of ways, and we can structure a deeper understanding and a clearer picture of it as we study the Scriptures and related literature. When discussing the duties of a pastor, the apostle Paul uses the term ἐπίσκοπος in his letters to Timothy and Titus. This phrase is frequently translated as "bishop." A better term to use would be overseer, which has the definition of "a man charged with the duty of seeing that matters to be completed using others are completed rightly, any curator, guardian, or superintendent" according to Strong's Concordance. Therefore, a pastor is the one who oversees the affairs of God, a steward of the nearby church the place he or she has been called to serve and oversees the affairs thereof (Meloni and Bashirov,2023).

Cnaan points to the idea that an overseer is a manager of God's house, which is the local church, and not the owner of it (Cnaan, and Scott,2021). Another author also sees the pastor as one having oversight on the household of God, which he understands to be the local church (Darko,2023). The pastor as an overseer of the church is to be concerned with the entire well-being of the church and its functions(William Bryan,2024) As a steward of God's affairs, the pastor manages the household of God, looking after the members of the local church (White,2022) Smith demonstrates how an overseer, being in a position to observe every aspect of the local church's functioning, does more than focus on just one aspect of its operations. Rather, they assume a leadership role. By assuming such a role, the pastor can make sure that every aspect of the church is functioning cooperatively toward the organization's objectives and mission (Gregory,2019)

Reasons Why Church People Criticize Pastors

If you serve in a church, criticism comes with the territory. I doubt that any pastor or leader likes it. But, we must deal with it in a God-honouring way. One way to do that is to understand why people criticize pastors. Below are some of the reasons why church people criticize pastors

1. ***They lack Spiritual Maturity:*** Some people criticize pastors because they think it's part of a Christian's job description. After all, "Pastors need to avoid pride and some good healthy criticism can keep them humble."
2. ***They feel they are Losing the Church they Once Knew:*** As we get older, we must deal with the inevitable results of ageing, slowing cognitive function, and reduced flexibility and resilience. Seniors in your church

may feel that the changes you are bringing are taking away the church they grew up in.

3. ***They don't feel they have a voice:*** Some church people can feel that their opinions don't matter and so criticize pastors to get their voices heard.
4. ***They don't deal with change very well:*** Some people are born more adverse to change than others. Their brains are wired that way. Their fear circuits are more easily set off by uncertainty, and change brings uncertainty.
5. ***They need to find something or someone toward which to vent their hurt caused by other life issues:*** Some people in your church project their hurts through criticism. Criticism helps ease their angst, at least for the short term.
6. ***They are truly Malevolent People Committed to your Demise:*** Although I believe these critics are few, they do exist. If you face this kind of person in your church, take bold action. Sometimes extreme cases require you to apply church discipline.
7. ***They have a Point:*** Sometimes the criticism is valid and you need to hear it. Response: Listen and heed. When the criticism reflects a valid issue, learn from it and make appropriate adjustments in your life or ministry." Criticism is never pleasant, but sometimes necessary (Stone,2023).

Pastoral Leadership and its Critics

Every pastor and other church leader have critics. No church leader can avoid the pain of criticism. Dealing with critics is one of the biggest challenges pastors face in ministry. You can't eliminate the pain of criticism, but you can deal with it constructively. One way to solve this problem is to try your best to understand how the critic thinks. By doing so, church leaders can also respond pastorally. Let us take a look at these five types of critics in the Church

1. ***The Constructive Critic:*** This person truly wants what is best for you and the church. He or she has no personal agendas or vendettas. Most of them prayed about talking or writing to you before they met you. The best response is to listen, recognize, and change if necessary. The problem is that it is often difficult to discern a voice of constructive speaking amid a cacophony of other criticism.

-
2. ***The Negligent Critic:*** This person says careless things and doesn't think much about it. He doesn't realize that his words hurt you. He didn't make it a personal issue. I made a critical comment in a leadership position and had no idea it was so hurtful. And I would never have known my mistake if other people hadn't told me. If you tell these critics your complaints, they will be amazed and repent
 3. ***The Hurt Critic:*** Suffering is widespread in the world, and church members are not immune to it. Because of their suffering, these critics often lash out at pastors in moments of deep frustration and anger. Unfortunately, pastors are often the most visible and convenient targets for hurt and angry critics. If pastors can recognize the thinking of these critics, they should have two responses. First, you should not take criticism personally. Second, we must make every effort to respond with compassion, consideration, and love.
 4. ***The Sinful Critic:*** Some believers live in rebellious and unrepentant sin. Their criticism is an attempt to change course. They refuse to confront their rebellious behaviour, so they try to make you feel guilty. If a pastor notices that there is an unrepentant sin in a member's life, he should confront him about it. Unfortunately, pastors often fail to recognize this when they are criticized.
 5. ***The Self-serving Critic:*** This critic is showing a poorly concealed irritation because the church does not get his way on some matters. He doesn't like music. He does not approve the budget voted on by the church. Someone changed "their" order of service. So he is attacking you because you are the leader who initiated or embraced these changes. These critics are in many ways the most difficult people. Pastors and other church leaders would do well to consider two basic ways to deal with critics. First, recognize that criticism is inevitable. Anyone in a leadership position will be subject to criticism. Address it prayerfully and courageously, but embrace it as part of your leadership so that it never goes away.

Second, try to figure out what type of critic you are dealing with. In many cases, criticism will help you in your life and ministry. In other cases, we may deal with critics in a pastoral and redemptive way. Any criticism hurts. At least most of us do. But not all criticism is harmful to us. Indeed, in many cases, our leadership and ministry can be more effective if we deal with critics in more redemptive ways (Research.lifeway.com,2016)

Positive Effects of Criticism on Pastoral Leadership

Criticism is a form of communication

When someone gives you criticism, it means they want to give you feedback about the work you are doing for them. This means you can learn more about the people you're working with and how to turn them into satisfied customers, churchgoers, or audience members. Think for a moment before responding to what they say. In business, working with people who are patient and able to accept and respond to criticism means both parties can work towards better results. For a theatre, production or pastor, this may mean finding out what the audience/congregation wants.

1. ***Criticism gives Feedback:*** If you always think you're right but don't get feedback from others, how can you be sure that what you're doing is good? Whether you're selling or speaking, whether it's a product or a service, getting honest feedback and acting on it will help you know exactly what's good and what's better. Use this information to make changes to our performances, services, exhibitions or events. This may sometimes be uncomfortable to hear, but it can ultimately make your product, service, conference, etc. stronger.
2. ***It forces you to think about how you work:*** Constructive criticism can break you away from bad habits and move you toward good ones. Try to be objective and look at what you are offering as if it were not yours. This can be especially difficult when you're deeply involved in a project, but taking a step back can help you see how you can improve the way you work and avoid negative outcomes in the future. Did you need a more specific explanation? Did you miss anything in the early stages of the project? Is the performance deadline too unrealistic?
3. ***The right kind of criticism can give you an advantage:*** Think about it: if you can get a customer or Church member to tell you and just you – how to give them the perfect product or service, that's information you've got that no one else has. That puts you at an advantage over anyone else in your sector and can be used again in the future to get things right, even faster. Find ways to squeeze that information from your client or audience and get them to tell you what they want (Thomas, 2012). The above explanations on the positive effects of criticism on pastoral leadership show that a pastor without criticism cannot go far in the ministry. Therefore, we must also consider the negative effects of criticism on pastoral leadership, namely:

Negative Effects of Criticism on Pastoral Leadership

Criticism Destroy

Destructive criticism is also regarded as an unavoidable nuisance, especially if it involves a personal attack on others. The goal of destructive criticism is to destroy the criticized target by making destructive criticism. For example, you should close your business or church and look for a job. The target is to show that the other person's point of view lacks merit and has no validity in the eyes of anyone. Destructive criticism is often criticized because it has a more destructive effect than a positive one. The term "destructive criticism" means that the intensity or scope of criticism varies depending on how destructive it is. People tend to believe that criticism goes to the point of destroying things. This is an example of an argument continuing to escalate, turning into an argument, getting out of control and everyone starting to turn against each other. In this case, the criticism is exaggerated. What started as a conversation ended in closure and turned into destructive criticism? Destructive criticism from authority figures such as parents causes psychological damage to children, which affects their self-esteem, behavioural performance, and social acceptance, and causes children to grow up with a lower self-image. Additionally, destructive criticism from spiritual leaders, church members, wives, etc. causes psychological damage to pastors, which affects their self-esteem, sermons (Bhasin,2019)

History of the Redeemed College of Missions, Ede

The Redeemed Christian Church of God established a mission school as a branch of Redeemed Christian Bible College with three students in 1993 at Olowoobida, Ede. Due to its rural and urban location, Ede was chosen from three sites selected for the school. Later, in the year 2000, in particular, the college moved to its permanent location at Ededimeji, Ede, Osun State in South-western Nigeria, where there is ongoing development of physical structures, human lives, and spiritual giants to this day. RCM aims to teach Christians who have a strong calling and conviction to engage in cross-cultural missions in both rural and urban areas. These individuals would employ all communicative means to share the gospel with people everywhere (Oke, 2022). The institution currently has 35 staff members, more than 10 adjunct instructors, and has over 200 students. Some of these leaders (Staff members, students and adjunct lecturers) hold various leadership roles within the church, which may subject them to various forms

of criticism. In addition, the Redeemed Christian Church of God is one of the biggest, most well-known, and wealthiest churches in Nigeria, and her pastors, like other divine ministers, face criticism. State.

Pastoral Leadership and Criticism in the Redeemed College of Missions, Ede

Leadership is an exciting yet exhaustive venture of faith. Like all institutions worldwide, particularly sacred institutions where individuals are trained for spiritual assignments, the leaders and trainers at the Redeemed College of Missions also face their share of criticism. These criticisms often target various aspects of leadership, including teaching abilities, personality traits, and children's behaviors. Some leaders have been criticized for their training approaches, with certain trainees perceiving them as excessively strict. Although missions training may inherently involve difficult elements, leaders' attempts to implement various training exercises have sometimes resulted in criticism from students. However, it is crucial to recognise that criticism is inevitable for any leader, regardless of how perfect one might consider oneself to be. The aim of this paper is to assess Pastoral Leadership Response to Criticism in the Redeemed College of Missions, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria.

Results and Discussion of Findings

This chapter presents the results, data analysis, and discussion of findings. The paper addresses three key questions: How do spiritual leaders respond to criticism? What are the most criticized aspects of pastoral leadership? And what are the effects of criticism on pastoral leadership? Data for each research question was analysed using simple descriptive statistics and frequency tables, suitable for the questionnaire-based study involving 141 respondents out of the intended 150. Participants included trainers, parish pastors, students, adjunct lecturers, and members of Emanuel Missions at the Redeemed College of Missions, Ededimeji, Ede. They were purposively and randomly selected. Questionnaires were administered physically and online via WhatsApp and Google Forms. The analysis was divided into demographics (sex, age, marital status, place of conversion, ordination, position, and experience) and statements on criticism of pastoral leadership.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Gender of the Respondents

The study sought information on the sex of the respondents. Table 1 presents a summary of the sex of the respondents

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents' Gender

Gender	Frequency	%
Male	87	61.7
Female	48	34
Nonresponse	06	4.3
Total	141	100.0

Source: Fieldwork Data, 2023

Out of the 141 respondents, 87 respondents representing 61.7% of the sample represented male while 48 respondents which constitutes 34% represented the female participants. This may be because the sampled college used has more male occupants than female occupants. However, 6 respondents represented 4.3% did not indicate their age. This may be an oversight.

Respondents' Age

The study sought information on the age of the respondents. Table 2 presents a summary of the age of all the respondents.

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents' Age

Age Group	Frequency	%
15-20 years	11	7.8
21-30 years	47	33.33
31-40 years	48	34.04
41 & above	33	23.4
Nonresponse	02	1.42
Total	141	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

A close look at the respondents in table 4.3 shows that,11(representing

7.8%) respondents are within the age 15-20,47(representing 33.33%) are within the age of 21-30,48 respondents (representing 34.04%) are within the age of 31-40 while 33 respondents (representing 23.4%) are within the age of 41 years and above. This clearly indicated that many respondents were mature and experienced enough to respond to issues on criticism of pastoral leadership. However, 2 respondents (representing 1.42%) did not indicate their age.

Marital Status of the Respondents

The study sought information on the marital status of the respondents. Table 3 presents a summary of the marital status of the respondents.

Table 3: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents' Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	%
Single	84	59.6
Married	55	39
Divorced	-	-
Others	01	0.7
Nonresponse	01	0.7
Total	141	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Out of 141 respondents,84 respondents (representing 59.6%) are single,55 respondents (representing 39%) are married, none of the participants are divorced and only 1 respondent (representing 0.7%) fall on the group of others. This indicated that, majority of the respondents are single and married However,1 respondent (representing 0.7%) did not indicate his/her marital status.

Respondents Ordination Status

The study sought information on the Ordination Status of the respondents. Table 4 presents a summary of the Respondent's Ordination Status.

Table 4: Respondents Ordination Status

Ordination Status	Frequency	%
Pastor	12	8.51

Asst. Pastor	09	6.38
Deacon	17	12.06
Deaconess	14	9.93
Unordained minister	58	41.14
Member	24	17.02
Nonresponse	07	4.97
Total	141	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4.5 shows the titles of respondents for the study; the result revealed that 12 respondents (representing 8.51%) are pastors, 9 respondents (representing 6.38%) are assistant pastors, 17 respondents (representing 12.06%) are deacons, 14 respondents (representing 9.93%) are deaconesses, 58 respondents (representing 41.14%) are unordained ministers, 24 respondents (representing 17.02%) are church members. This indicates that the largest participants are unordained ministers. However, 7 respondents (representing 4.97%) did not indicate their ordination status. This may be an oversight.

Respondents' Position in the College

The study sought information on the position of the respondents in the College. Table 5 presents a summary of the Respondents' Position in the College.

Table 5: Respondents' Position in the College

Position in the College	Frequency	%
Trainer	25	17.73
Student	102	72.34
Church Members outside/inside the college	07	4.97
Adjunct lecture	05	3.55
Nonresponse	02	1.42
Total	141	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 5 shows the demographic characteristics of Respondents' Position in the College. The result revealed that 25 respondents (representing 17.73%) are trainers, 102 respondents (representing 72.34%) are students, 7 respondents (representing 4.97%) Church Member from outside and inside the college, 5 respondents (representing 3.55%) are adjunct lecturers. This shows that the larger percentage of the respondents are students (Some of them have been a parish pastor before coming to the college of missions). However, 2 respondents (representing 1.42%) did not indicate their position in the college.

Respondents Years of Work Experience

The study sought information on the Respondent's Years of work experience from only pastors and those who occupy spiritual leadership. Table 6 presents a summary of the Respondents Years of work experience

Table 6: Respondents Years of Work Experience

Years of work experience	Frequency	%
1-5	14	41.18
6-10	08	23.53
11-20	08	23.53
21-30	01	2.94
31 & above	-	-
Nonresponse	03	8.82
Total	34	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 6 shows the ranges of years of working experience in the sampled respondents for the study; the result revealed that 14 respondents (representing 41.18%) are within 1-5 years, eight (8) respondents (representing 23.53%) are within 6-10 years, eight (8) respondents (representing 23.53%) are within 11-20 years, one (1) respondent (representing 2.94%) are within 21-30 years, none of the participants indicated for 31 years and above. The table clearly reveals that respondents are experienced spiritual leaders. However, 3 respondents (representing 8.82%) did not indicate their years of work experience.

Presentation of Research Questions

Research Question One: How do Spiritual Leaders react/respond to criticism?

To answer the Research question above Table 7 below is used.

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics on How Spiritual Leaders react/respond to criticism

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	NR (%)	TO TA L (%)	Ra nk
1.	My leaders' response to criticism is characterized by hostility	13(12.15)	38(35.51)	37(34.58)	17(15.89)	02(1.87)	107(100)	4 th
	My leaders' response to criticism is characterized by calmness	31(28.97)	51(47.67)	14(13.08)	10(9.35)	01(0.94)	107(100)	5 th
2.	My leaders' response to criticism is characterized by calmness	08(7.48)	20(18.69)	46(42.06)	31(28.97)	02(1.87)	107(100)	1 st
	My leader does not respond to criticism at all	37(34.58)	60(56.07)	07(6.54)	07(6.54)	2(1.87)	107(100)	3 rd

-
4. My leader responds to criticism occasionally
 5. How criticism is framed usually influences the leader's interpretation and responses
-

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 7 presents descriptive statistics on how spiritual leaders respond to criticism in the Redeemed College of Missions, Ede. Findings show mixed reactions. About 48% of respondents agreed that leaders sometimes respond with hostility, while 50% disagreed. A larger majority (77%) agreed that leaders respond with calmness. Only 26% believed leaders do not respond to criticism at all, while 71% disagreed, indicating that leaders generally do respond. Furthermore, 69% agreed that leaders respond only occasionally, suggesting responses are not consistent. Finally, 85% agreed that the way criticism is framed influences leaders' interpretations and reactions, showing they respond differently to constructive and destructive criticism. A small number of respondents did not indicate their opinions across statements.

Research Question Two: What are the most criticized aspects of pastoral leadership?

To answer the Research question above Table 9 below is used.

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics on the most criticized aspects of pastoral leadership

S/N	Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	NR (%)	Total (%)	Rank
1.	Church doctrine	46(42.9)	45(42.0)	11(10.2)	05(4.6)	01(0.9)	107(100)	1 st
2.	Children of clergy	33(30.8)	49(45.7)	17(15.8)	07(6.5)	01(0.9)	107(100)	3 rd
3.	Clerics' wives	46(42.9)	41(38.3)	17(15.8)	02(1.8)	02(1.8)	107(100)	2 nd
4.	Pastors' wealth	35(32.7)	44(41.2)	17(15.8)	09(8.4)	00	107(100)	4 th
5.	Pastors' anointing							

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 8 presents descriptive statistics on the most criticized aspects of pastoral leadership. The findings show that church doctrine is the most criticized, with 85% of respondents agreeing. About 77% agreed that clergy children are also commonly criticized. Similarly, 74% reported that clerics' wives face frequent criticism. Pastors' wealth is another major concern, with 81% agreeing it is often criticized. Lastly, 74% indicated that pastors'

anointing also attracts criticism. A small percentage of respondents did not state their opinions across items. Overall, the most criticized areas include church doctrine, clergy children, clerics' wives, pastors' wealth, and pastors' anointing.

Research Question Three: What are the effects of criticism on pastoral leadership?

To answer the Research question above Table 10 below is used.

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics on the effects of criticism on pastoral leadership

S/N Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	NR (%)	Total (%)
1. I'm always hurt whenever I'm criticized	03(8.82)	18(52.94)	09 (27)	04(11.77)	----	34(100)
2. Criticism has provided helpful feedback for me in the past.	13(38.24)	17(50)	6.47	02(5.88)	----	34(100)
3. Criticism has ruined my self-image and seriously damaged my self-esteem before	05(14.71)	11(32.35)	02 (5.88)	06(17.65)	----	34(100)
4. I was once criticized and it resulted into	02(5.88)	14(41.18)	12 (35.29)	06(17.65)	----	34(100)
	02(5.88)	12(35.29)	12 (35.29)	16(47.06)	----	34(100)
	01(2.94)	18(52.94)	5.29		----	34(100)

	conflict,			10(29.4	----	
	anger,	13(38.24)	17(50)	1)	----	34(100)
	resentment,				--	
	withdrawal,			14		
	stress and			(4	06(17.6	
	anxiety.	12(35.29)	19(55.88)	1.1	4)	----
5.	I had			8)	----	
	experience				--	
	raised B P					
	in the past	11(32.35)	19(55.88)	10	-----	34(100)
	because of			(2	----	
	criticism.			9.4	----	
6.	Criticism			1)	--	
	had					
	wounded my				01(2.94	
	precious)		
	pride before			09		
				(2	----	
7.	Criticism			6.4	----	
	had hurt my			7)	-----	--
	sense of					
	importance					
	and aroused					
	resentment			04	----	
	in me in the			(1	----	
	past			1.7	-	
8.	Criticism			7)		
	has guided					
	me away					
	from bad				----	
	practices				----	
	and towards			02	----	
	good ones			(5.	--	
				88		
9.	Criticism)		
	from my					
	congregation					
	had made					
	me a more					

competent	04
preacher	(1
10. Criticism	1.7
had helped	7)
me to be	
more	
prayerful	
and serious	
with the	
study of	
God's word.	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 9 presents the descriptive statistics on the effects of criticism on pastoral leadership in the Redeemed College of Missions, Ededimeji, Ede. The results show that 62% of respondents admitted feeling hurt when criticized, while 38% did not. A large majority (88%) stated that criticism has provided helpful feedback in the past. However, 47% reported that criticism once damaged their self-image and self-esteem, though 53% disagreed. Similarly, 47% experienced criticism leading to conflict, anger, resentment, withdrawal, stress, or anxiety, while 53% did not. Only 12% reported raised blood pressure due to criticism, while 88% disagreed. About 41% said criticism wounded their pride, whereas 59% disagreed. Additionally, 56% felt criticism once hurt their sense of importance, while 44% disagreed. Positively, 88% agreed that criticism guided them away from bad practices, and 91% said it made them more competent preachers. Finally, 88% stated that criticism strengthened their prayer life and commitment to Bible study.

Discussion of Findings

This section discusses the study's findings on criticism of pastoral leadership in the Redeemed College of Missions, Ededimeji, Ede, Osun State. Table 7 shows how spiritual leaders respond to criticism, indicating that leaders use different response patterns at various times. Some respondents affirmed that certain leaders react to criticism with hostility. Researchers support this by noting that collaborative or confrontational strategies can help leaders advance their agenda, while avoidant or

persuasive strategies are less effective (Putri, Putri, Eryanto, & Adha, 2023). However, most respondents indicated that their leaders are not hostile, aligning with scholars who advise leaders to handle criticism with resilience, reflective responses, and by distinguishing between personal and role-based critiques (Nawaz, 2019).

Regarding calm responses, respondents agreed that their leaders often react calmly to criticism. This supports scholarly recommendations that leaders should prepare constructive responses such as, “Thank you for sharing your point of view; I’ll consider it”. Most respondents also agreed that leaders usually respond to criticism, although a few indicated non-response. Research similarly notes that destructive criticism can lead individuals to confront or avoid, with avoidance sometimes intensifying conflict (Harvey, Taylor, Regmi, & Van Teijlingen, 2022).

Findings further show that leaders respond to criticism occasionally, meaning they do so when necessary, although a minority believe leaders respond more consistently. Importantly, respondents affirmed that the framing of criticism significantly influences leaders’ interpretation and responses. Scholars agree that the critic’s state of mind affects how criticism is framed and how leaders react, as well as the clarity of the message delivered (Xing, Sun, Jepsen, & Zhang, 2023). In summary, leaders generally respond to criticism when needed, display both calmness and occasional hostility, and are strongly influenced by how criticism is framed. Table 8 presents findings on the most criticized aspects of pastoral leadership in the Redeemed College of Missions, Ede. Respondents indicated that church doctrine is one of the most frequently criticized areas, consistent with scholars who note that doctrinal and theological controversies have long shaped the church’s development (Paul & Richard, 2013).

The children of clergy are also heavily criticized. Research shows that Pastors’ Kids (PKs) are among the most visible and scrutinized individuals in the church. They often face judgment regarding their appearance, friendships, academics, and behaviour. In one survey, PKs ranked criticism as their greatest disadvantage (253 times) and constant observation as second (181 times). Many also experience increased exposure when parents use them in sermon illustrations (Margareth, & Gunawan 2021).

Similarly, the cleric’s wife is often criticized. Studies reveal that pastors’ wives frequently endure unrealistic expectations, church conflicts,

intrusions into family life, and lack of privacy, leading to silent suffering within ministry contexts (Moore, Williams, & Cooper, 2022). Regarding pastors' wealth, respondents agreed it is a major point of criticism. Finally, pastors' anointing is also criticised. Researchers emphasize the need to evaluate signs and wonders by examining whether they glorify God, reflect godly character, and strengthen the faith community (Mtavangu, 2018). In conclusion, the most criticized areas of pastoral leadership include church doctrine, clergy children, clerics' wives, pastors' wealth, and pastors' anointing.

Table 9 presents data on the effects of criticism on pastoral leadership in the Redeemed College of Missions, Ededimeji, Ede. Criticism can wound a person's pride, hurt their sense of importance, and arouse resentment. Skinner demonstrated that rewards are more effective than punishment in creating lasting behavioral change, a principle applicable to humans as criticism often breeds resentment (Nwagbara, & Belal. 2019).

Regarding personal reactions, most respondents reported feeling hurt when criticized, consistent with scholars noting that emotional responses and relational outcomes vary by source and individual differences (Kufa, 2021). Criticism has also provided helpful feedback for many, improving performance and encouraging reflection. Conversely, fewer respondents agreed that criticism had damaged self-esteem or led to conflict, suggesting that spiritual maturity mitigates negative effects. Only a small number reported physical effects such as raised blood pressure from criticism, indicating low physiological impact for most. Criticism has wounded the pride of some respondents and hurt their sense of importance, provoking resentment.

Positively, criticism guided 88.24% of respondents away from bad practices, while 91.17% reported that criticism from their congregation improved their preaching competency. Additionally, 88.23% stated that criticism encouraged greater prayerfulness and diligence in studying God's word. These findings highlight that while criticism can be painful, when constructive, it enhances personal growth, spiritual maturity, and professional competence, emphasising the value of embracing feedback for development.

Conclusion

The study concludes that pastoral leaders at the Redeemed College of Missions, Ededimeji, Ede, Osun State, react to criticism in different ways, mostly calmly, though some may respond with hostility. How they respond depends largely on how the criticism is presented, and while most address criticism when necessary, a few avoid it, which can worsen conflict. The areas most criticized are church doctrine, children of clergy, clerics' wives, pastors' wealth, and pastors' anointing, reflecting both personal and institutional scrutiny. Criticism can hurt pride and cause resentment, but spiritual maturity helps reduce its negative impact. Constructive criticism, however, has clear benefits: it corrects bad practices, improves preaching, and encourages prayerfulness and deeper study of God's word. Overall, criticism, though sometimes painful—can promote personal, spiritual, and professional growth when handled wisely.

Recommendations

Based on the findings discussed, this study recommends that:

1. Religious leaders (in the College of Missions Ede) should embrace calmness strategy of response to criticism regardless of the manner in which the criticism is framed by the followers. But criticism should address firmly when necessary. These will assist the leaders to enlist the aids of his/her followers to obtain a common goal.
2. Christian leaders should ensure that their wives and children present themselves as a role model for others. Their teaching and demonstration of the anointing should have biblical support. This will reduce the level of criticism.
3. Leaders should make use of criticism, whether constructive or destructive, for the growth of their personal lives and their institutions. They should not allow criticism to kill their enthusiasm.

References

- Allred, K. M., & Chambless, D. L. (2018). Racial differences in attributions, perceived criticism, and upset: A study with Black and White community participants. *Behavior Therapy, 49*(2), 273–285.
- Andersen, B. (2022, September 16). Four benefits to embracing constructive criticism. *LinkedIn*. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/four-benefits-embracing-constructive-criticism-brad-andersen>

- Ayogu, S. O., Ribeiro, J. L., & Leite, R. (2022). Practising servant leadership: Pastoral and social ministry in the modern age. In C. Machado (Ed.), *Challenges and trends in organizational management and industry*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-98048-1_2
- Bhasin, H. (2019). 18 different types of criticism. *Marketing91*. <https://www.marketing91.com/18-different-types-of-criticism>
- Brown, V. L. (2010). Biblical guidance for effective pastoral leadership. *Academia.edu*. <https://www.academia.edu>
- Bryan, G. W. (2024). Developing a small group discipleship model through the expository preaching at Macedonia Baptist Church, Kuttawa, Kentucky. https://hdl.handle.net/10_39_2/6102
- Chandra Sekhar Rao, V. (2020, January). A brief study of criticism and its forms. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339139621_A_Brief_Study_of_Criticism_and_Its_Forms
- Cnaan, R., & Scott, M. (2021). Personality, prosperity, priority, productivity, and piety: Selecting congregational valued lay leaders. *Journal of Health and Human Services Administration*, 43(4), 382–405. <https://doi.org/10.37808/jhhsa.43.4.4>
- Contemporary dictionary. (2020). *Cambridge Dictionary*. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary>
- Dennis, E. E., Romm, A. N., & Ottaway, J. (1990). The case for constructive criticism of the press. *Newspaper Research Journal*, 11(2), 2–10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/073953299001100202>
- Ecomium. (2017). 5 major criticisms that hover over Pastor Adeboye. <https://encomium.ng/5-major-criticisms-that-hover-over-pastor-adeboye>
- Gregory, T. (2019). Transformational pastoral leadership. *Journal of Biblical Perspectives in Leadership*, 9(1), 56–75. https://www.regent.edu/acad/global/publications/jbpl/vol9no1/Vol9Iss1_JBPL_4_Gregory.pdf
- Hans, F. (1998). *Empowered leaders: Ten principles of Christian leadership*. Nashville, TN: W. Publishing Group.
- Harvey, O., Taylor, A., Regmi, P., & van Teijlingen, E. (2022). Struggling to reply to reviewers: Some advice for novice researchers. *Health Prospect: Journal of Public Health*, 21(2), 19–22. <http://eprints.bournemouth.ac.uk/37248>
- Holy Bible: Easy-to-Read Version, Revised Edition. (1987, 1999, 2005). World Bible Translation Center.
- Igbari, O. (2021). Jesus’ model of leadership and the integrity of church leaders in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Christian Studies*, 4(1). <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/njcs/article/view/220842>
- Kufa, T. (2021, January 5). Negative effects of criticism: A summary from *How to make friends and influence people*.

<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/negative-effects-criticism-summary-from-how-make-friends-kufa>

- Lee, C., & Rosales, A. (2020). Self-regard in pastoral ministry: Self-compassion versus self-criticism in a sample of United Methodist clergy. *Journal of Psychology and Theology, 48*(1), 18–33.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0091647119870290>
- Margareth, J., & Gunawan, W. (2021). The relationship between perception of father parenting style and religiosity of the adolescent pastor's children. *Veritas: Jurnal Teologidan Pelayanan, 20*(2), 277–295.
<https://www.ojs.seabs.ac.id/index.php/Veritas/article/view/493>
- Mahaney, C. J. (2022). The pastor and personal criticism.
<http://www.cjmahaney.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/The-Pastor-and-personal-Criticism.pdf>
- Meloni, M., & Bashirov, G. (2023). The 'government of men': Moving beyond Foucault's binaries. *Economy and Society, 52*(4), 719–741.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/03085147.2023.2256582>
- Moore, D. D., Williams, C., & Cooper, C. E. (2022). Pastoral leaders' perceptions of mental health and relational concerns within faith-based organizations. *Journal of Pastoral Care & Counseling, 76*(2), 80–88.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/15423050221081476>
- Mtavangu, E. (2018). The doctrine of biblical miracles in Christian theology.
https://www.academia.edu/37387718/The_Doctrine_Of_Biblical_Miracles_in_Christian_Theology_Autosaved
- Nawaz, S. (2019, July 10). How to take criticism well. *Harvard Business Review*.
<https://hbr.org/tip/2019/07/leaders-need-to-learn-how-to-take-criticism>
- Nwagbara, U., & Belal, A. (2019). Persuasive language of responsible organisation? A critical discourse analysis of corporate social responsibility (CSR) reports of Nigerian oil companies. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal, 32*(8), 2395–2420. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AAAJ-03-2016-2485>
- Oke, A. I. (2022). Effect of parents lifestyle on the upbringing of children [Unpublished B.A. project]. Department of Christian Religious Studies and Philosophy, Redeemers University, Ede, Osun State.
- Pastoralcareinc. (2022, December 21). How to deal with criticism.
<https://www.Pastoralcareinc.com/resources/how-to-deal-with-criticism>
- Paul, S. R., & Richard, M. D. (2013, January 24). Dealing with doctrinal issues in the church: Proposal for ground rules.
<https://www.adventistarchives.org/dealing-with-doctrinal-issues-in-the-church-%E2%80%94-proposal-for-ground-rules.pdf>
- Putri, A. Q. K., Putri, F. A., Eryanto, H., & Adha, M. A. (2023). Understanding of visionary leadership and leadership ethics in organizations: Qualitative

- study. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi, Perkantoran, dan Akuntansi*, 4(2), 217–225. <https://journal.unj.ac.id/unj/index.php/jpepa/article/view/41497>
- Reed, J. (2020, August 12). How to react to different types of criticism: the good, the bad and the downright ugly. <https://authorjoannereed.net/how-to-react-to-different-types-of-criticism-the-good-the-bad-and-the-downright-ugly>
- Rutherford, S. (2007). Some selections by Mack Tomlinson of Texas from Rutherford's *The Loveliness of Christ*. Banner of Truth. <https://banneroftruth.org/us/resources/articles/2007/samuel-rutherfords-riches>
- Saleh, M. M., Nusari, M., Ameen, A., & Alrajawy, I. (2018). Leadership in the organization: A conceptual review. *International Journal of Management and Human Science (IJMHS)*, 2(4), 52–59. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328738899_Leadership_in_the_organizationA_ConceptualReview
- Scheleken, H. L., Bok, G. J. H., de Jong, H. L., van der Schaaf, F. M., Kremer, D. J. W., & van der Vleuten, P. M. C. (2021). A scoping review on the notions of assessment as learning (AaL), assessment for learning (AfL), and assessment of learning (AoL). *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 71, 101094. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2021.101094>
- Skinner, B. F. (1938). Reinforcement theory. <https://www.potentialunearthed.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/Reinforcement-Theory.pdf>
- Solomon, D., & Theiss, J. (2022). *Interpersonal communication: Putting theory into practice* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/97811351174381>
- Thomas, M. (2012, February 9). Six reasons why criticism is a good thing. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/culture-professionals-network/culture-professionalsblog/2012/feb/09/reasons-tips-criticism-arts>
- van Houtum, A. E. M., Geert-Jan, W., Wever, C. M., Janssen, H. C., van Schie, C., Tollenaar, S., & Elzinga, M. (2022). Adolescents' affective and neural responses to parental praise and criticism. *Developmental Cognitive Neuroscience*, 54, 101099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcn.2022.101099>
- Vanguard. (2018). Why I don't reply my critics. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2018/12/why-i-dont-reply-my-critics-adeboye>
- White, A. G. (2022). Setting the boundaries: Reading 1 Timothy and Titus as community charters. *Biblical Theology Bulletin*, 52(4), 242–252. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01461079221133447>
- Wisniewski, B., Zierer, K., & Hattie, J. (2020). The power of feedback revisited: A meta-analysis of educational feedback research. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 3087.

<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.03087/full>

Xing, L., Sun, J. M., Jepsen, D., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Supervisor negative feedback and employee motivation to learn: An attribution perspective. *Human Relations*, 76(2), 310–340. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00187267211038514>